

Focus Group and Survey Report on the Role of Libraries During Crises in Estonia

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Abstract:	This report presents findings from Estonia for WP2A2 of the Caelum project, focusing on the role of university libraries during crises and their contribution to civic engagement and community resilience. Based on a survey and a focus group with the academic library, university staff and students, the analysis highlights key challenges, expectations, and opportunities related to crisis response, information support, and mental health services.
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Executive Summary

This report presents the key findings from the Estonian case study within the Caelum project, which explores the role of university libraries during crises. It is based on data gathered through a focus group discussion with students, academic staff, and library professionals, as well as an online survey conducted among Estonian higher education community. Together, these methods offer valuable insights into how libraries have responded to past crises, what expectations different stakeholder groups have for libraries in times of disruption, and what challenges affect their ability to respond effectively.

The findings are thematically structured around the project's research questions (RQs), addressing libraries' current and potential roles in crisis situations, perceived user needs, institutional limitations, and opportunities for civic engagement. Particular attention is given to the role of libraries in supporting students' mental health during crises, as this is the focus of the University of Tartu's selected case study, which will be explored in greater depth in the next phases of the project.

The report highlights several good practices, such as maintaining emotional continuity through stable library environments, offering informal support through empathetic staff and calm spaces, and providing access to reliable information. The report concludes with practical suggestions for how libraries could strengthen their crisis response capabilities and better support their communities.

About the project

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response, 2025-2027, <https://caelum.ut.ee/>) is a 2-year Erasmus+ project that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-UA cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to up-skill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response. Thus, CAELUM empowers university libraries in leveraging open and citizen science approaches as well as community engagement practices for crisis response in multiple contexts.

1. Introduction

This report presents the findings of Activity 2 within Work Package 2 (WP2) of the CAELUM project, which investigates the role of libraries during times of crisis. The aim of this activity is to gather firsthand perspectives from individuals connected to higher education (students, academic staff, and library professionals) on how libraries respond to crises and what roles they are expected to play.

To collect these insights, a mixed methods approach was used, combining qualitative and quantitative data collection through a focus group discussion and a survey. This approach enabled the research team to explore both firsthand experiences and broader expectations about library services in crisis contexts.

Crises, as defined in this study, refer to a time of great danger, difficulty, or doubt when problems must be solved, or important decisions must be made (Oxford University Press, n.d.). These may include experiences such as a global pandemic, war or armed conflict, political turbulence, economic hardship, climate-related emergencies, or information-related challenges like disinformation or information overload.

Libraries, particularly those within universities, are uniquely positioned to support communities during such times. As highlighted by Lison (2024), libraries have undergone a transformation from passive information providers to dynamic community anchors promoting resilience, trust, and social cohesion. In unstable contexts, such as the war in Ukraine or the COVID-19 pandemic, libraries can function as inclusive spaces where individuals find not only information but also connection, a sense of community, and both emotional and academic support (Lison, 2024).

This report explores how libraries have responded to past crises, what kind of support users expect, and how libraries may contribute to building more resilient, informed, and connected communities in the future.

1.1. Research Questions

To explore the role of libraries in times of crisis, the CAELUM consortium collaboratively developed a set of core research questions. These questions served as the foundation for both the data collection instruments and the subsequent analysis.

The research questions were as follows:

RQ1: What has been the libraries' role during crises?

RQ2: What are the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, and library professionals regarding library support in crisis situations?

RQ3: What barriers and gaps have university libraries faced in responding to crises?

RQ4: How can university libraries contribute to public engagement and community resilience during and after crises?

While the questions were designed to ensure consistency across all partner institutions, each partner also had the opportunity to formulate additional questions aligned with their forthcoming case studies under Work Package 3 (WP3). This allowed them to gather context-specific insights relevant to their focus areas in preparation for upcoming project activities.

In the context of Estonia, the University of Tartu Library (UTL) is conducting its case study with a focus on the library's role in student well-being. UTL looks to find and map potential actions that academic libraries can take to improve students' mental health and help them better cope with mental health crises. Based on that, a fifth research question was added:

RQ5: How can the library support students' mental health?

This additional question aligns with the UTL case study aims and will provide guidance in developing pilot projects during the case study implementation in WP3.

1.2. Participants

Based on the project application, the study participants included students, academic staff, administrative support staff, and library staff. These groups were selected as they are directly involved with academic libraries.

The focus group consisted of five participants: two library professionals, one academic staff member, one administrative/support staff member, and one student. Given the small number of participants, a separate figure was not included for the focus group.

The survey received responses from a total of 65 individuals. However, three respondents did not provide consent to participate, resulting in 62 valid responses.

Figure 1. Survey respondents' current role in the academic community (n = 62).

As illustrated in Figure 1, most respondents were library staff (n = 35), followed by administrative or support staff (n = 10), students (n = 9), and academic staff (n = 8). No respondents indicated having a role outside of the predefined categories listed in the survey. The respondents represented a broad age range. The largest group was between 35 and 49 years old (n = 27), followed by those aged 50 and over (n = 20). Respondents aged 25–34 made up a smaller portion (n = 11), while only a few were under 25 years old (n = 4).

Although the number of participants from each target group was not evenly distributed, all key stakeholder groups were represented in the study. This allows for a more diverse understanding of the library's role in crises.

1.3. Methodology

To address the proposed research questions, a mixed-methods approach was employed, combining quantitative and qualitative data collection through an online survey and a focus group discussion.

1.3.1. Survey

An online survey was disseminated from the 19th of May until the 31st of May using Microsoft Forms. The survey questions were jointly developed by all CAELUM project partners and then translated into Estonian to ensure accessibility. The final questionnaire was available in both Estonian and English, allowing participants to choose their preferred language when responding. To test the clarity and internal coherence of the translated version, the questionnaire was piloted with two respondents before broader distribution. The survey was

then promoted through multiple channels such as university mailing lists, UTL social media channels and to other university libraries in Estonia.

The survey included both closed and open-ended questions. The closed-ended questions focused on gathering quantifiable data about participants' expectations, perceived barriers, and views on the role of academic libraries during crises. These responses were analyzed using basic descriptive statistics. For multiple-choice questions, results are presented as counts and percentages to illustrate the main trends. For questions that used a rating scale, the analysis includes both the mean and the standard deviation, which reflects how much individual responses deviate from the average (Rootalu, 2014). A low standard deviation indicates a high level of agreement among respondents, while a higher value points to a broader diversity of opinions (Rootalu, 2014).

The open-ended questions allowed participants to share their experiences and expectations more thoroughly. These responses were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and insights that add depth to the quantitative results. The full list of survey questions can be found in [Annex II](#).

1.3.2. Focus Group

A single focus group was conducted on the 23rd of May 2025 with five participants and two moderators. The group brought together individuals representing diverse roles within the academic community, including one student, academic staff, library professionals, and support personnel. A purposive sampling strategy was used, whereby participants were deliberately selected from the academic community to ensure a variety of perspectives.

The discussion was held online through Zoom and followed a semi-structured interview guide developed collaboratively by CAELUM project partners. Each partner had to follow the agreed upon structure but were allowed to ask further questions which focused on their specific case study. The full list of questions used in the focus group can be found in [Annex I](#).

The session was conducted in Estonian, recorded and later transcribed with a public speech recognition service of TalTech's Laboratory of Language Technology tekstiks.ee (Olev & Alumäe, 2022). After transcription, the data was anonymized. All quotes presented here were translated into English.

The qualitative data from the focus group was analyzed using thematic analysis which aims to identify and interpret patterns of meaning within the data (Braun & Clarke, 2006). Rather than merely describing what participants said, the analysis focused on systematically identifying meanings, establishing connections, and interpreting recurring patterns considering the research questions.

Following Braun and Clarke's (2006) recommendations, the analysis began with a close reading of the transcript to gain a comprehensive overview of the discussion. The transcript was then examined in detail, and meaningful segments of text were coded using labels that closely reflected the content. Coding was done manually using Excel. Codes addressing similar ideas or themes were grouped together to develop potential thematic categories. In the next phase, these categories were reviewed to ensure they reflected meaningful patterns across the transcript. The final themes were formulated with the aim of linking the coded extracts to the topics raised in the research questions.

1.3.3. Ethical considerations

All participants were informed of the aims of the study and provided informed consent before participating in either the focus group or survey. The data collection process complied with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the University of Tartu's internal data protection policies. Personal data were anonymized and focus group consent forms were stored separately from the data. Participants were given one week to withdraw their consent. The audio recording and consent forms related to the focus group were permanently deleted after transcription was completed. Access to raw data was restricted to the research team at the University of Tartu, and only anonymized findings were used in analysis and reporting.

2. Findings

This chapter presents the results of the study, following the structure of the research questions. To provide a comprehensive overview, the findings from the focus group and survey are presented together under each thematic subsection. The chapter begins with a background section that outlines which crises respondents referred to and how they typically seek information during such events.

2.1. Background

This subchapter provides an overview of the types of crises that have affected members of the academic community and the information sources they turn to in such situations. These insights help contextualize how libraries are positioned within broader crisis responses.

Survey participants were first asked which types of crises had most affected them. The most common answer was the pandemic or health crisis (n = 30), followed by war or armed conflict (n = 14) and mental health or well-being challenges (n = 10). The distribution of responses is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Distribution of crises experienced by survey respondents (n = 62).

In the focus group, all participants first named the pandemic, and several also mentioned the war in Ukraine. Interestingly, one library professional described a library renovation as a crisis, referring to the uncertainty and frequent changes it brought to the work environment.

Participants also described the emotional impact of these crises: initial feelings of anxiety, fear, and uncertainty were common, often followed by a shift toward reflection and the desire to help others. As one librarian explained:

"At first, you feel that your sense of security is disturbed... you feel anxious, unsure... but once that fear is overcome, you start thinking about others, those more vulnerable, those in need."

This evolving emotional response was also reflected in concrete responsibilities. Another librarian recalled how, during the pandemic, libraries were expected to ensure public access to state e-services, even while staff themselves faced the same crisis. Libraries across Estonia had to quickly find ways to provide internet access beyond their physical spaces and help people access government information and digital services, such as the 1247 crisis helpline. As the librarian noted, this experience revealed the need for clearer guidance and procedures in advance, so that libraries could act more effectively when a crisis hits.

Survey participants were next asked how they usually find information during crises. The most common source was news media (n = 55), followed by government websites (n = 29), social media (n = 23), and friends or family (n = 22). Only a few respondents reported using library channels (n = 4), and two mentioned other sources, such as a doctor or general internet searches (e.g., Google). The distribution of responses is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Information sources used during a crisis by survey respondents (n = 62).

These results suggest that in times of crisis, people primarily turn to mainstream media, official government channels, and their personal networks for information. Academic and university

sources are also used, but to a lesser extent. Libraries were mentioned only rarely, indicating a potential gap in visibility or perceived relevance during crisis situations.

Since the most frequently mentioned crises were the pandemic and the war, it is likely that many of the responses about library support are linked to experiences during these two major events.

2.2. Library Roles During Crises

This section explores people’s current experiences with academic libraries during times of crisis. The aim was to understand how different members of the academic community perceive the library’s role in supporting them, what help they have received, and which crises have shaped these experiences.

Participants were asked whether they had ever received support from a library during a crisis. Most participants had not experienced this (n = 31), while fewer answered yes (n = 17) or were unsure (n = 14). The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 4 as percentages.

Figure 4. Experience of receiving library support in a crisis by survey respondents (n = 62).

If the response was yes, they were asked to bring examples. Those who had received support described a variety of experiences, which varied slightly depending on their role in the academic community. Library staff most often mentioned access to reliable information and emotional support through routine and continued services: *“I looked for reliable information and entertainment”* and *“Being in a familiar routine helps maintain emotional balance.”* Administrative and support staff highlighted the stabilizing effect of the library remaining open: *“The continuation of library services provides a sense of security.”* A student respondent

emphasized the emotional value of safe access to books during the COVID-19 pandemic: *“The ability to safely order books home and read online during COVID created a sense of human security.”* Although not many have had experiences with support from the library in a crisis, these examples illustrate how libraries can provide both emotional and practical support.

To better understand the potential role of libraries in future crises, survey participants were also asked what types of support they would expect from a library during a crisis. The most selected options were access to curated information (n = 50), charging stations (n = 49), internet or Wi-Fi (n = 48), and online library services, such as e-books and databases (n = 39). Also frequently chosen were physical space for study or work (n = 42) and mental health support or a safe environment (n = 31).

Other forms of support included emergency supplies, such as masks or flashlights (n = 25), cultural events and opportunities for social interaction (n = 21), training sessions and courses (n = 20), and guidance for using academic databases (n = 17). Less commonly expected was help with government forms or aid (n = 15) and support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis (n = 15). No respondents indicated that they would not expect anything from a library. One respondent mentioned a former nuclear bunker at the library that could serve as a short-term shelter, though its condition and functionality were unclear to them. The full distribution of responses is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Forms of support expected from libraries during a crisis (n = 62).

These results align with the focus group discussion, where participants repeatedly emphasized the importance of reliable information, especially during the early days of a crisis. One library staff member stated:

"The main thing I would want is trustworthy information, behavioral guidelines, not something I'd read on Facebook but from a single clear source."

Several participants envisioned the university library as a potential crisis center, offering electricity, information, and a safe gathering space. A researcher noted:

"The university library could absolutely act as crisis information centers... it has physical space, access to information, and people who are ready to help. That potential is already there."

Concrete examples, particularly in the context of the war in Ukraine, included initiatives such as creating a "Ukraine room," sharing reliable sources through the library website, and organizing a book fair to raise funds for Ukrainians.

In addition to practical and informational functions, participants highlighted the library's role in offering emotional support during crises. While not always labeled as mental health services, activities like therapy dogs, bibliotherapy, or simply providing a safe and welcoming space were seen as meaningful forms of support. These aspects are explored in more detail in section 2.6.

Overall, the findings suggest that while participants expect basic practical support, like internet, information, and physical space, there is also a strong desire for libraries to offer emotional resilience, community connection, and low-threshold mental health support during crises.

2.3. Expectations and Needs

This subchapter explores the types of support that members of the academic community expect from libraries during crises. It highlights perceived priorities, desired services, and suggestions for how libraries could better respond to future challenges.

2.3.1. Survey results

Survey participants were asked to rate the importance of a variety of needs that may arise during crises, using a five-point Likert scale (1 = not at all important, 5 = very important). These needs covered both traditional library functions (e.g., access to information and infrastructure) and broader forms of support (e.g., community connection, emotional well-being, or opportunities for collaboration). The results indicate a clear prioritization of informational and infrastructural support, with emotional and community-related needs rated more variably, as reflected in higher standard deviations.

The most important needs according to the aggregated results were emergency information updates (mean = 4.6, standard deviation = 0.9), followed closely by access to credible, accurate, and curated information (M = 4.5, SD = 0.9). These were rated consistently high across

respondents, reflecting the fundamental role libraries play as trusted information providers in times of uncertainty.

Next in priority were infrastructural needs, such as reliable internet access ($M = 4.3$, $SD = 1.0$) and access to physical space or shelter ($M = 4.3$, $SD = 1.1$), which emphasizes the library's role as a stable and accessible environment during disruption. Online library access ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 1.1$) and the need to feel informed and involved ($M = 3.9$, $SD = 1.1$) were also rated highly, which suggests that people expect libraries to keep digital services running and to help them stay connected and informed during a crisis.

Social and emotional support services were ranked lower overall. Community connection, being part of the solution, and opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others all shared a mean rating of 3.5 ($SD = 1.4$), indicating that while some respondents value these, they are not a priority for most. Support for mental health was rated slightly lower ($M = 3.3$, $SD = 1.3$), which is still above the midpoint of the scale but shows considerable variation among respondents. Help with digital tools received the lowest score ($M = 3.0$, $SD = 1.5$). This suggests that these kinds of support are either seen as less important for libraries or that opinions about them vary a lot between different groups.

2.3.2. Differences by Respondent Role

A comparison by respondent group revealed distinct patterns in how different academic community members perceive the role of libraries in crisis response. While group-level means are reported to highlight these differences, standard deviations are omitted from the text for readability. However, across most categories, responses showed a high degree of variation, especially regarding emotional and community-related needs.

Students consistently assigned high importance to both informational and emotional support needs. They rated credible information ($M = 4.6$), and emergency updates ($M = 4.2$) highly but also gave above-average scores to feeling informed and involved ($M = 4.0$), support for mental health ($M = 3.2$), and community connection ($M = 3.4$). This suggests that they see the library not only as a place for information, but also as a source of emotional and social support during crises.

Academic staff also gave high ratings for information-related services, such as emergency information ($M = 4.3$), curated content ($M = 4.3$), and internet access ($M = 4.1$). However, they placed less importance on support-related needs. For example, mental health support received a mean score of 3.0, and collaboration opportunities received 3.1. This suggests that academic staff tend to see the library's role in crises as mainly supporting the continuation of academic work.

Library staff demonstrated a more comprehensive and balanced understanding of the needs libraries could meet. Their average scores were high across nearly all categories, including emergency information updates (M = 4.7), internet access (M = 4.5), and physical space (M = 4.5). They also placed above-average importance on mental health support (M = 3.3) and community connection (M = 3.7). This suggests that they see the library as having a broad role in both the institution and the wider community.

Administrative and support staff gave the highest ratings across almost all needs. They especially valued emergency updates (M = 4.9), physical space (M = 4.8), curated information (M = 4.6), and internet access (M = 4.4). Notably, they also rated emotional and participatory needs highly, with most scores averaging above 4.0. This suggests that they see libraries as fully integrated parts of crisis preparedness and response, who can support academic work, but also infrastructure and emotional well-being.

2.3.3. Focus group results

The focus group discussion confirmed and added depth to the survey findings by showing how people experience and understand library support during crises. Participants talked about the emotional comfort they felt from the library's routines and familiarity. Being able to borrow books or use digital services helped them feel more stable and in control. Although all participants were connected to the academic library, they stressed the importance of being able to borrow fiction to ease stress.

"And actually, during COVID, people really wanted entertaining reading as well. One part is studying, of course, but another is easing your anxious thoughts by reading fiction. Libraries lent out a lot of fiction through the pickup lockers during that time."

This feeling of stability was also linked to the library space itself. The conversation focused on the comfort of consistent routines and the emotional impact of having a quiet, accessible space. One participant said the sudden closure of the university library made it hard to focus or study; it had been a personal refuge for them. When the library reopened, it helped them get back into their study routine. A student described the library as *"a place where I feel good,"* which suggested that past experiences made it safe for them during challenging times.

Library staff also played a significant role. One staff member said that during the pandemic, people would sometimes contact the library just to talk. Another recalled how the team quickly made plans to keep services running for students, driven by a shared sense of purpose and care.

Participants also said they trusted the library as a reliable source of information. One person described libraries as key in fighting disinformation, misinformation, and conspiracy theories.

"I was also thinking about the role of the library as an institution where information experts work, people who help fight disinformation, misinformation, and conspiracy theories. A place that shows people where and what reliable sources are that could help them. I do not think there are many such institutions in society, and in that sense, the library is a leading institution."

This perspective suggests that the library does not only function as an information provider but also plays a significant role in guiding people to reliable information and building public trust. This matches the survey results, where curated and emergency information were seen as some of the most valuable kinds of support.

While collaboration or digital skills were not widely discussed, one participant stressed the importance of technology. They noted that without digital tools and tech support, it would be much harder to help people effectively during crises like the pandemic.

Overall, the focus group supported the survey's results and showed that the library is not just a place for information, but also a steady and comforting place during a crisis. While participants described many positive experiences, some also pointed out challenges and limitations, which are explored in the following section on barriers and gaps.

2.4. Barriers and Gaps

This section identifies the main reasons that prevent libraries from fully supporting their communities during crises. Although libraries are often seen as trusted and accessible, both personal doubts and practical issues can affect whether people feel comfortable seeking support. To explore this, participants were asked how likely they would approach a library in a crisis and what might stop them.

Most respondents said they would feel comfortable seeking help from a library (n = 42), but a third (n = 19) were unsure. Only one respondent said they would not feel comfortable. The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 6 as percentages.

Figure 6. Perceived comfort in turning to libraries for crisis support (n = 62).

Those who answered “No” or “Not sure” were asked to explain. Based on their answers, the main barrier was uncertainty. Respondents often did not know whether the library could offer relevant help in a crisis or whether such support was part of the library’s role. As one person explained, *“I’m not sure what kind of help I could ask for, or who I’d even turn to in the library.”*

This lack of clarity was echoed in the focus group, where several participants expressed concern over the ambiguity of the library’s role in crisis support. As one librarian put it, *“We have a nice image that we can handle everything. But real life gets in the way sometimes.”* Another noted the emotional burden this expectation creates:

“Actually, this ability to provide mental or emotional help... maybe library staff should have some sort of first aid training for this because eventually it becomes emotionally very draining, and you don’t know how to help the person.”

This emotional toll was further emphasized by the recognition that library staff, like users, are also affected by crises: *“I’m a victim too, so why should I be doing extra work?”*

Expectations of mission-driven behavior also emerged as a barrier. There was a sense that librarians are assumed to step in out of moral duty, regardless of whether crisis support is part of their official role. One librarian explained, *“There is this assumption that whatever we do, it will somehow help because it is coming from a librarian. But that is not necessarily the case.”* These role conflicts and emotional strains were not captured in the survey but offer important context for interpreting hesitancy in turning to libraries for help.

In addition to exploring general attitudes toward seeking help from libraries, participants were asked what might prevent them from using library services during a crisis. The most common

barriers were the library being closed (n = 59), lack of internet access (n = 39), and difficulty in finding up-to-date information on the library’s website or social media channels (n = 29). A considerable number also noted that they did not know the library could help (n = 26) or that the library’s location was hard to reach (n = 26). The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Barriers to seeking help from a library in a crisis (n = 62).

These infrastructural challenges align with concerns voiced in the focus group. For example, one librarian highlighted the problem of technological lag in libraries and how that connects to chronic financial limitations:

“One clear problem is the technological lag [...], and that immediately leads to the next issue: financial limitations. It always seems to come down to there being no money.”

Participants also pointed to the lack of preparation and training as a key structural gap. While libraries were quick to respond during the pandemic, one librarian stressed that more could be done proactively: *“All of this is prevention work. It should be done now; a group of people should be trained in advance in peacetime.”* However, such training efforts require both time and financial investment, which is not available.

Finally, both survey and focus group data revealed that the library’s image may influence its perceived approachability. One respondent described the university library as having *“a kind of elitist aura,”* which could discourage some people from seeing it as a space for help, especially if they are not connected to the university. Similar sentiments were echoed in the open-ended survey responses. One participant noted, *“I’ve never had the impression that the library could offer that kind of help,”* while another wrote, *“The library is not the first place I would turn to in a crisis.”*

Some respondents saw the library as a place for studying, not somewhere to get emotional or practical help. This shows that many people do not yet see the library as a place to turn to during a crisis. Others mentioned hesitation tied to personal factors: *“I don’t know what kind of help I could even ask for,”* or *“I wouldn’t know who to turn to in the library.”* These views suggest that both the institutional image and lack of clear communication about library services can make it harder for people to see it as a supportive or welcoming place during a crisis.

2.5. Public Engagement and Community Support

This subchapter looks at how academic libraries connect with their wider communities during crises. It looks at how people perceive the library’s role in public outreach, what kind of activities they have participated in, and what support they expect, and what support they expect in challenging times.

Survey respondents were asked to rate their agreement with the statement *“Libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises”* using a five-point Likert scale ranging from *Strongly disagree* to *Strongly agree*. The results showed a high overall level of agreement (mean = 4.4, SD = 0.7).

However, when asked whether they had personally participated in any community-focused activities at their university library, the responses were more varied. Just under one-third (n = 20) answered yes, while over half (n = 32) said no, and 16% (n = 10) were unsure. The distribution of responses is presented in Figure 8 in percentages.

Figure 8. Participation in community focused events at the library (n = 62).

This suggests that although the idea of libraries as community hubs is supported in theory, it may not be fully realized in practice. Among those who had taken part in such activities, the examples included a wide range of cultural and informal events. These included exhibition openings, music evenings, seminars, therapy dog visits during the Night Library, and volunteering (e.g., helping clean books after renovations). Other responses referenced seasonal events, festivals, or mental health workshops hosted in the library. A few participants also mentioned hanging out with friends or just enjoying the atmosphere during these events. Although many examples were shared, some respondents expressed uncertainty about what counts as a community-focused event. This suggests that these types of initiatives may not be always clearly communicated to the public or recognized as part of the academic libraries' mission.

2.5.1. Expectations for Community Support During Crises

When asked what activities or services libraries could offer to support their communities during challenging times, survey participants provided a wide range of suggestions. These responses reflected both practical needs and emotional or social expectations.

A recurring theme was the need for clear and proactive communication. Several respondents emphasized the importance of timely and accessible information about what kind of support the library offers during crises. Suggestions included distributing leaflets, updating social media and websites, and sending emails to readers about available services. As one person noted, *"Share more information about what the library offers during a crisis, whether you can get direct help there, etc."* Another respondent stressed that it is also important to communicate that the library is a welcoming space for all community members, including international students and LGBTQ+ youth.

Accurate and trustworthy information remained a top priority, echoing earlier survey findings. Respondents suggested that libraries could play a role in addressing misinformation, provide crisis-related reading materials, and organize public events focused on mental health or social preparedness. One focus group participant emphasized that libraries are among the few institutions staffed by "information experts," positioning them as leaders in the fight against disinformation.

Providing a safe and welcoming space was also a frequently mentioned expectation. Participants envisioned libraries as physically and emotionally supportive environments where people could take shelter, rest, or find temporary relief from stressful conditions. Some respondents saw the library as a potential cooling or heating station, a place with electricity and internet during outages, or simply *"a space where you can feel a bit normal again."*

Notably, several responses from the survey and focus group emphasized the importance of mental health support, whether through offering a calm and inclusive atmosphere, inviting

therapy animals, or hosting anxiety-related workshops. There was also interest in maintaining informal human contact: *"Just being there"* or having *"empathetic and trained staff"* was seen as meaningful support. This is a positive signal for the case study the University of Tartu Library is planning to undertake, which will specifically focus on student mental health support during crises. These themes will be examined in more depth in section 2.6.

In sum, although the responses varied, the common underlining expectation was that the library could serve as a flexible, supportive, and trustworthy institution during times of uncertainty. However, some responses also reflected a degree of uncertainty or hesitation. Several respondents said they did not know what to suggest or were not sure what the library was already doing. This may point to a communication gap where people might believe in the library's potential role, but not fully understand what the role currently looks like.

2.6. The Library's Role in Supporting Student Mental Health

This subchapter takes a closer look at how libraries are perceived to support student's mental health during crises, drawing on both survey and focus group results. Although not rated as a top priority in the survey, mental health was explored in greater depth due to its relevance for the University of Tartu's case study focus.

Both the survey and focus group data suggest that academic libraries are perceived as having a meaningful role in supporting student mental health during crises. This support does not primarily stem from formal mental health services, but rather from the emotional, spatial, and informational stability that libraries offer.

In the survey, participants were invited to consider a broad range of potential needs during crisis situations (see Figure 5). Among these, mental health support was rated as important ($M = 3.3$, $SD = 1.2$) by many respondents, though it did not emerge as one of the most highly prioritized needs when compared to access to information or infrastructure. Still, over a third of respondents considered it relevant, and several open-ended comments emphasized the importance of *"empathetic staff," "a calm environment,"* and *"space where you can feel normal again."* This suggests that while not always seen as a top priority, mental well-being remains a recognized part of the library's broader support role.

The focus group discussion confirmed this. A university researcher pointed out that the University of Tartu Library has, over the years, already developed several services and spaces that contribute to mental well-being, even if they are not always recognized as such. Examples included the Night Library initiative with therapy dogs, the student kitchen area, and the presence of greenery throughout the building. The music department was also mentioned as a resource, where visitors can listen to music of their choice through headphones. These are not necessarily standard features in all libraries and have been introduced gradually over the

past two decades. The researcher emphasized the importance of highlighting these existing efforts. As a new idea, they also suggested creating a space where students could engage in creative activities to relieve stress related to academic work.

These findings reflect a broader understanding that mental health support is not limited to counseling services. Instead, it can also be expressed through environment, design, and informal human connection.

Besides that, human connection remained important. One library staff member shared that during the pandemic, patrons sometimes contacted them just to talk and relieve their worries about what was happening in the world. An empathetic listener could often provide relief in a stressful situation. Another example was a form of poetry therapy, in which librarians discreetly placed poems between borrowed books, allowing readers to encounter unexpected moments of reflection and calm.

However, several participants felt that the public and the wider university community are not always aware of these efforts. As a librarian said,

"The library must take on the role of constantly repeating this message, because every year new students arrive who do not know what services we have offered for a long time. The library needs to take an active role and promote itself."

This suggests that libraries do not only need to expand or refine services that support student mental health but also need to communicate them more clearly. Participants felt that making such support more visible could increase trust and usage while reinforcing the library's relevance for students.

When asked who the library should collaborate with to strengthen its mental health support role, focus group participants suggested working more closely with the university's counseling center and the University of Tartu Student Union. This was seen to better align services with students' actual needs and increase visibility through shared initiatives.

Finally, participants emphasized the importance of the library as a space for togetherness and peer support.

"The library also serves as a place to be together, to collaborate with others. So again, the opportunity to talk to each other, to study together, to laugh together, to cry together - in fact, the library has a significant role in making sure this kind of space exists, where people can come together and work side by side."

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3. Conclusion and recommendations

This study explored how academic libraries, with a focus on the University of Tartu Library, are perceived as community support institutions during times of crisis. The results indicate that while libraries are viewed as trustworthy and supportive spaces, their potential roles in crisis response and mental health support are not yet fully defined or consistently recognized by their users.

The findings show that participants appreciate the stability, routine, and calm that libraries offer during crises. Libraries were described as emotionally grounding environments where access to reliable information and the ability to maintain academic routines provided a sense of control. Specific initiatives such as the Night Library, therapy dog visits, or placing poetry in borrowed books were mentioned as meaningful contributions to emotional well-being, even if their impact is often understated.

At the same time, uncertainty emerged as a consistent barrier. Many survey respondents were unsure whether the library could or should offer support in crisis situations. Open-ended responses revealed limited awareness of existing services, and a lack of clarity about what kinds of help might be available. While libraries are often associated with information provision, their role as spaces for emotional support is less clearly understood by users.

In addition to these perceptual and communicative challenges, several practical limitations also surfaced. The most frequently mentioned obstacles included the library being closed, lack of internet access, or difficulty in finding up-to-date information online. Some respondents also noted the library's physical inaccessibility or were simply unaware that the library could offer help. These infrastructural barriers are just as important as issues of perception or communication. They have a direct impact on whether users can or want to turn to the library during a crisis and must therefore be taken seriously when planning improvements to crisis preparedness.

From the institutional side, focus group discussions highlighted the emotional demands placed on library staff, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic. Participants expressed concern about burnout and ambiguity in role expectations, noting that while the mission to help is often strong, it must be balanced with clear boundaries and adequate resources. There was a shared sense that libraries are expected to "be everything" without sufficient systemic support.

Community engagement was broadly supported in principle, but less consistently realized in practice. Survey participants agreed that libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises, yet many were unsure whether they had participated in community-oriented events. Focus group insights suggested that such activities are often not framed or

communicated as community engagement, even when they serve that function. Respondents called for more visible communication about available services, especially for new student cohorts, and emphasized the importance of inclusion, particularly for international students and minority groups.

Mental health was a recurring concern throughout the study. Although not the highest-rated need in the survey, qualitative data suggest that libraries are valued for their indirect contributions to emotional well-being. Focus group participants called attention to spaces and services that already support mental health, such as greenery, the student kitchen, and the music room, but noted that these efforts are not always made visible. Suggestions for improvement included creating creative activity zones and enhancing collaboration with the university counseling center and student union.

Overall, the study suggests that libraries are seen as capable of supporting their communities during crises, but that their role needs to be more clearly communicated, internally supported, and strategically developed. The following recommendations are based on these findings:

1. Clearly define how the library supports users during crises, including its role in emotional and mental well-being. Share this understanding with both staff and users.
2. Actively promote current services that support mental health, such as the Night Library, green spaces, the music department, etc. Emphasize their benefits through regular outreach and collaboration with the student union.
3. Offer basic training in emotional support or crisis communication for staff. Also acknowledge the emotional labor involved in frontline library work during crises.
4. Develop areas where students can relax or do creative activities to ease stress. Make these spaces inclusive for all users.
5. Make mental health services and spaces more visible. Label them clearly and include them in regular communication, especially at the start of the academic year.
6. Cooperate with the university counseling center and student union to better meet student needs. These partnerships can also help avoid duplication of services.
7. Clearly communicate what the library offers during crises. Make service information easy to find and update regularly. Use simple messages to help new users understand what kind of support is available and who they can turn to.

These steps can help academic libraries move toward a more intentional and resilient role in crisis response, one that not only offers access to information, but also provides meaningful emotional and community support.

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Annex I

Focus Group Discussion Questions

Background and role

Brief introduction of participants and their role in the academic community.

I Experience with Crisis Contexts

What kinds of crises have you experienced or thought about?

How have these situations affected your research or personal life?

Where would you turn first for help in a crisis, and why?

II Library Roles During Crises

Do you consider libraries as trusted institutions in your community? Why or why not?

Have you ever received help or support from a library during a crisis?

How did the library respond (or could have responded) to the crisis during that time?

III Expectations and Needs

If such a crisis occurred tomorrow, what kind of support would be most important to you?

What would you expect from your library in this situation?

IV Barriers and Gaps

What are the main barriers that prevent libraries from supporting people in this specific crisis?

Are there reasons why you or others might not seek help from a library? If yes, how could we change it?

V Public Engagement & Community Resilience

Can you imagine a library being a place for community action or support? If yes, then how?

In your opinion, how can libraries build stronger communities during or after a crisis?

VI Case Specific Questions

How could the library support students' mental health?

What do you think the library could offer? What services should we develop?

With whom should the library collaborate to support students' mental health?

Annex II

Survey Questions

I Background information

1. Age *(select one option)*

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-60

61+

Prefer not to say

2. What is your current role within the academic community? *(Select the one you identify with the most)*

Student

Academic staff (e.g., lecturer, researcher)

Library staff

Administrative or support staff

Citizen scientist

I am not a member of the academic community

Other: _____

3. What type of crisis has affected you the most? *(Select one option)*

War or armed conflict

Political turbulence

Pandemic or health crisis

Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life

Information overload and challenges related to open science in research

Climate related crisis (e.g., heatwave, drought, flooding)

Disinformation during emergencies (e.g., war, disasters)

Problems with social integration or job opportunities for international students

Barriers faced by disabled people (e.g., access, inclusion)

Other: _____

4. How do you usually find information during a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

Social media

News media

Government websites

University websites or communication

Friends/family

Library channels

Academic journals or research sources

Other: _____

II Library Roles During Crises

5. Have you ever received support from a library during a crisis? Support could include practical help, information, or emotional support. *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

5a. If yes, what kind of support did you receive? *Open question*

6. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library? *(Select all that apply)*

Access to curated information

Internet or Wi-Fi

Charging stations

Physical space for study/work

Mental health support or safe environment

Cultural events and social interaction

- Help with government forms or aid
- Emergency supplies (masks, flashlights, etc.)
- Online library services (ebooks, databases, etc.)
- Guidance for using academic databases
- Training sessions and courses
- Support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis
- I would not expect anything from a library
- Other: _____

III Expectations and Needs

7. When facing a crisis, how important would each of the following be for you personally? Some of these needs may be supported by libraries, others may not. Please rate how important each would be to you personally in a crisis. (Rate each from "Not at all important" to "Very important")

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Access to credible, accurate, and curated information					
Reliable internet access					
Access to physical space or shelter					
Community connection					
Support for mental health					
Online library access					
Emergency information updates					
Assistance with digital tools					
Being part of the solution					
Opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others					

Feeling informed and involved					
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8. What would make a library feel like a supportive and safe space during a crisis (e.g., space, staff, resources)? *Open question*

IV Barriers and Support Gaps

9. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis? *(Select all that apply)*

Library is closed

Difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels

Library location is hard to reach

Library is not accessible or inclusive for disabled users

Library has no internet access

Did not know library could help

Negative past experiences at the library

Lack of trust in libraries

Other: _____

10. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis? *(select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

10a. If you answered “No” or “Not sure,” please explain why:

Open question

V Public Engagement and Community Support

11. Do you agree with the following statement: Libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

12. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

12a. If yes, what kind of activity or event was it? *Open question*

13. What activities or services could a library offer to support your community in difficult times? *Open question*

14. Do you have anything to add? *Open question*